

Identifying disease specific gait kinematics using wearable sensors: knee versus hip osteoarthritis

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Abstract: Monitoring disease progression of degenerative disease of lower extremity joint forms the basis for large clinical trials elucidating the effects of interventions aimed at improving physical function. Technical advancements in wearable sensor technology are promising for obtaining digital data on joint function during daily activities. In this paper, we present promising data on disease specific gait alterations in patients with knee or hip osteoarthritis compared to age-matched controls measured with wearable sensors.

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I. Introduction

Knee and hip osteoarthritis (OA) are very common diseases that will affect 25% of the population in the course of a lifetime [1]. Yet, to date diagnostics for early OA are lacking and its treatment is difficult. The development and investigation of interventions such as pharmaceuticals is challenging as clinical trials currently rely on outcomes that are either subjective (e.g., patient reported outcome measures – PROMs) or have insufficient sensitivity for detecting short term changes (e.g., medical imaging). Hence, there is a great need for quantitative outcomes that reflect the functional status in patients with knee or hip OA.

The potential of gait analysis in understanding the OA disease process and its treatment has long been recognized [2]. While the literature has largely focused on ambulatory load in the context of knee OA [3], differences in joint motion during walking between patients and controls have been observed [4,5]. Traditionally, ambulatory loading and joint motion is assessed in dedicated laboratories limiting the application in large scale clinical trials or routine clinical practice. The feasibility of using gait parameters as outcome parameters for clinical trials necessitates their simple measurement and specificity to the affected joint. The purpose of this study was to determine if gait kinematics specific to the disease – i.e. knee versus hip OA – can be identified using wearable sensors.

II. Material and methods

Twenty-three patients with unilateral knee OA before scheduled total knee replacement (11 women/12 men; age: 66±9 years; body mass index (BMI): 28.1±3.8 kg/m²), 24 patients with unilateral hip OA before scheduled total hip

replacement (10 women/14 men; age: 66±10 years; BMI: 27.5±3.2 kg/m²), and 28 age-matched asymptomatic persons (18 women/10 men; age: 69±6 years; BMI: 24.9±3.8 kg/m²) completed gait analysis with wearable inertial sensors on a 20-m walkway.

Figure 1: Placement of the inertial sensors.

Lower extremity joint kinematic data were collected with the inertial sensor system RehaGait® (Hasomed, Magdeburg, Germany) as described by Nüesch et al. [6]. In brief, for each participant, seven inertial sensors were placed bilaterally on the lateral foot, lateral lower leg and lateral thigh, and on the pelvis overlying the 5th lumbar vertebra using elastic straps (Fig. 1). Each sensor (dimensions: 60 mm×15 mm×35 mm) contains a triaxial accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer (magnetometer data not used in the proprietary software computations). The system and model were calibrated first with the subject standing in a neutral upright position for 10 s and then alternately lifting their legs and flexing their trunk forward. Spatiotemporal and kinematic time series

for the hip, knee and ankle were computed by the manufacturer's proprietary software (Hasomed, Magdeburg, Germany) according to Seel et al. [7]. Previous studies have shown good agreement of kinematic parameters with camera-based motion analysis (root mean square error of kinematic time series: $<5^\circ$; kinematics intraclass coefficients (ICCs) >0.967) [6], excellent agreement of spatiotemporal parameters with an instrumented treadmill (trivial difference: Cohen's $d < 0.2$) [8], and good to excellent reliability in healthy subjects (spatiotemporal: ICCs: 0.73–1.00; kinematics: limits of agreement kinematics test-retests, $<4^\circ$, ICCs >0.96) [6,8]. Spatiotemporal parameters and hip, knee, and ankle joint angle trajectories were compared between groups using t-tests and statistical parametric mapping (SPM) with t-tests for independent samples ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 2: Knee (left) and hip (right) flexion angles during walking at self-selected speed normalized to one gait cycle for patients with unilateral knee OA, unilateral hip OA and asymptomatic controls (top), SPM results (middle) and differences in joint angles for comparison between patients with hip OA and patients with knee OA.

III. Results and discussion

Patients with knee (0.95 ± 0.21 m/s) or hip OA (1.05 ± 0.21 m/s) walked slower than asymptomatic persons (1.24 ± 0.16 m/s; $P < 0.001$). Main kinematic differences between the affected leg in patients with knee OA and controls were less knee flexion during weight acceptance and throughout swing (-5° ; $P < 0.05$) without significant changes at the hip. Main kinematic differences between the affected leg in patients with hip OA and controls were less hip flexion during weight acceptance and midstance (-6°), and less hip and knee extension during push-off (-6° ; $P < 0.05$). Both groups had greater ankle dorsiflexion in terminal stance (knee OA, $+12^\circ$; hip OA, $+7^\circ$; $P < 0.05$).

Patients with knee OA had significantly smaller knee flexion during midstance and push-off (-13°) and greater knee flexion during weight acceptance ($+5^\circ$) and late swing ($+8^\circ$) compared to patients with hip OA in the respective affected leg ($P < 0.05$; Fig. 2).

In this study, we demonstrate not only that known kinematic patterns associated with knee [3] or hip OA [4] can be measured with a wearable inertial sensor system but also that these gait alterations are specific to knee or hip OA, respectively. Main kinematic differences to asymptomatic control subjects were observed at the respective index joint with lesser compensation at adjacent joints. These results point towards the potential of using gait analysis with wearable inertial sensors to help in the diagnosis of the primary disease site. This study represents an important step towards future use of kinematic gait parameters as outcome in clinical trials and for monitoring treatment success in patients with knee or hip OA. Moreover, observed changes at adjacent joints emphasize the importance of assessing overall kinematic changes to recognize the potential of developing OA at adjacent or contralateral joints because of compensatory mechanisms.

IV. Conclusions

The results presented here provide first evidence that disease specific alterations in gait patterns may be detected using wearable sensors. This approach should be expanded to large data sets and further explored with machine learning approaches to identify discriminant pattern features and determine the minimum number of sensors necessary.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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